

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN STUDENTS OF THE FACULTY OF LIGHT INDUSTRY AND CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY

Nuraliyeva Zarina Askar qizi

Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology,

Faculty of Light Industry and Chemical Technology, 1st year student

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, there is a growing interest in the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical technologies in education, one of the reasons for which to date students are taught only ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies requires them to think independently. teaches to search, analyze and draw conclusions.

Keywords: technology, multimedia, pedagogical technology, information technology, foreign language, trends.

В настоящее время возрастает интерес к использованию интерактивных методов, инновационных технологий, педагогических технологий в образовании, одна из причин, по которой на сегодняшний день школьников учат только готовым знаниям, а использование современных технологий требует от них осмысления независимо. учит искать, анализировать и делать выводы.

Ключевые слова: технологии, мультимедиа, педагогические технологии, информационные технологии, иностранный язык, тренды.

Today we cannot imagine our daily life without mass media as a whole in our society. Whatever area we talk about, these tools will not leave us. Information technologies are especially relevant in the educational process. It is widely used to expand the knowledge and horizons of young people through computer programs. In the teaching of various subjects, modern

information technology, which further increases the effectiveness of lessons. As in all areas of the country's social and spiritual life, comprehensive reforms have been carried out in the education system, including the introduction of information technology in the education system, the educational process of higher education. the quality of education and improve it

efficiency. Of great importance for teachers of the Uzbek language and literature is the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov dated May 13, 2016 "On the establishment of the Tashkent State University of the Uzbek language and literature named after Alisher Navoi".

Literary Analysis and Methodology. It is planned to conduct scientific research on new and effective methods of teaching the subject of literature, the widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies. Therefore, the subject "Modern information technologies in teaching the Uzbek language and literature" was included in the curriculum

University of Uzbek language and literature. The subject "Modern information technologies in teaching the Uzbek language and literature" is aimed at teaching information and communication technologies that can be used in teaching the Uzbek language and literature, methods of their use at the required level.

The purpose of teaching the subject is to equip future teachers of the Uzbek language and literature with the knowledge, skills and abilities to use modern information technologies in the classroom, provide information about the tools, requirements for resources prepared for Uzbek language lessons. language and literature, foreign experience in this area and the skills necessary for students to effectively organize the pedagogical process in the information age, the formation of a creative and technological culture. [1] Today, the requirement of the time is the ability of any science teacher to be able to create pedagogical software and use it effectively in the classroom.

The aforementioned science, which teaches how to improve the quality and

effectiveness of electronic materials used in the lessons of the Uzbek language and literature, serves to ensure a higher level of organization of the Uzbek language and literature classes.

Conclusions. As part of the study of the subject “Modern information technologies in teaching the Uzbek language and literature”, the student is expected to achieve the following results: and the tasks set;

- The structure of the information and educational environment;
- World experience in developing information technology skills;
- have an idea about the reform of scientific and educational research in the world of information technology;
- Importance of using information technologies in education;

Список использованной литературы

1. Шайкисламов, Н. (2020). Использование интерактивных методов на уроках родного языка. Перспективы развития науки и образования, 1 (2), 247-249.
2. Шайкисламов, Н. (2020). Использование современных педагогических технологий в обучении родному языку. Проблемы науки и образования в Узбекистане: проблемы и решения, (3), 71-73.
3. Шойназарова, Вазира Хушбаковна, and Сабохат Мамашукурова. "О ПЕРЕВОДЕ НЕКОТОРЫХ АНГЛИЙСКИХ ИДИОМ НА РУССКИЙ И УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК." Гуманитарный трактат 38 (2018): 14-15.
4. Shoynazarova, Vazira Khushbokovna, and Husniddin Bahritdinovich Ruziev. "Teaching english to young learners." Иностранные языки в Узбекистане,(3) (2019): 64-71.
5. Алаудинова Д. Theoretical approach of oral communication competency //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3/S. – С. 147-151.
6. Technology Of Teaching Languages AD RustamovnaJournalNX, 180-183, 2020

STEP KONFERENCA

